

STUDY ON THE DURABILITY COMPARISON OF STS316 NON-COATED AND TiN COATED FOR METALLIC BIPOLAR PLATE

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1. Introduction

Worldwide, energy consumption increased rapidly to improve the quality of life. And it will be accelerated, so oil price goes up continuously. In January 2008, oil prices have surpassed 100USD per barrel. [1]

In many developed countries, research on newly energy source has been promoted for a long time. Especially, fuel cells are being studied for applications of many fields. Among them, the case of PEMFC is very hard to apply in the transportation system.

The purpose of this study is to improve the durability of the metallic material bipolar plate for PEMFC by surface treatment instead of the traditional graphite material. [2~5]

2. Experimental

2.1 Specimen preparation

The specimen of this experimental is STS316 in austenite stainless steel. STS316 has normally application in the industrial field used common stainless steel. Specimen size was prepared 60^Lx60^Wx1.5^t mm, and machined for air and

hydrogen path multi-channel serpentine type only one place. Fig.1 shows the metallic bipolar plate schematic machined.

Fig. 1 Schematic of as-machined STS316 metallic bipolar plate.

2.2 TiN coating

PEMFC environment has a high acid corrosion condition. Normal metallic material has many corrosion tendencies in this environmental condition. Especially, STS316 has an excellent corrosion resistance on the acidic condition better than other stainless steel materials. Furthermore, STS316 specimen was coated with TiN using PVD process.

Mechanical wear property and corrosion resistance property were improved by TiN coating on the stainless steels. This experiment was applied to metallic corrosion resistance by a TiN coating on STS316 specimen. Because operating condition of PEMFC has a high acid environment.

Fig. 2 STS316 metallic bipolar plate coated with TiN.

2.3 Potentiodynamic Polarization

Potentiodynamic polarization test has a benefit to analysis corrosion property at laboratory. This experiment was used to the Solartron 1470E device. Measuring condition is the voltage from -0.2V to 1.0V, scan speed is 1mV/s, and reference electrode is Ag/AgCl, and it was saturated by KCl. Before experiment, electrode was purged by nitrogen gas for 30min. This analysis was used 3 times and got the average data.

2.4 Conductivity

Fuel cell has to require for good conductivity during the fuel cell operating condition. In addition, metal material has an excellent conductivity better than carbon material or carbon composite as a bipolar plate material.

In this experiment, the current source is Model 6220 DC precision current source (Keithley) and voltmeters used are Model 2182A nanovoltmeter (Keithley). This experiment was used four point probe process. Current range is from

-1×10^{-3} to 1×10^{-3} . Voltage measure range is 10mV. It is suitable that the DOE requires for this experiment target.

Fig. 3 Schematic for Potentiodynamic polarization analysis device

2.5 Single cell test

Evaluation of single cell test is an important experimental method to evaluate the durability of the fuel cell. In the case of single cell, the data was obtained from single cell test for 30 hours. Many researchers got data obtained from single cell test only for several minutes to several ten minutes level. So their electrochemical results were obtained in a short time, citing the possibility of a long predicted.

In this experiment, we need to analysis what is happened to single cell performance for these materials of bipolar plate increasing single cell operating time.

3. Results and discuss

3.1 TiN coating

TiN coating treatment has been made a new passive film on the STS316. As we have known, TiN coating process will be improved corrosion and wear resistance. In the experiment, we focus on the corrosion resistance properties for PEMFC metallic bipolar plate.

Fig. 2 shows TiN coated metallic bipolar plate. TiN coated specimen thickness is from 5µm to 10 µm.

3.2 Potentiodynamic polarization

Potentiodynamic experiments to predict the corrosion rate is a good experimental method. The results of this experiment are shown in Fig. 4.

I_{corr} value to determine the corrosion rate was similar between Non-coated and TiN coated STS316 specimen. However, TiN-coated specimen showed that I_{corr} is an excellent value.

The obtained results by using Tafel equation, Non coated STS316 has $3.60 \times 10^{-7} (A/cm^2)$. And TiN coated STS316 has $2.10 \times 10^{-7} (A/cm^2)$. TiN coated STS316 has excellent corrosion resistance value.

(a) Non-coated STS316 (b) TiN-coated STS316

Fig. 4 Result of polarization curves for Non-coated and TiN coated STS316 metallic bipolar plate.

3.3 Conductivity

The conductivity target from DOE is over to 100S/cm. In this experiment, Non-coated STS316 has 13120.5S/cm and TiN coated STS316 specimen has 13661.8S/cm. All kinds of specimens have excellent conductivity and these results show that TiN coated STS316 specimen is suitable for metallic bipolar plate of PEMFC.

3.4 Single cell test

During the 30 hours, current of Non-coated STS316 has a very low drop down from 0.50A to 0.45A on 0.6V condition. However, current of the TiN coated STS316 has more sharply dropped down from 0.8A to 0.6A on 0.6V condition.

Thus, initial single cell test, TiN coated STS316 specimen has a good passive film better than raw material STS316. Furthermore, TiN coated specimen has an excellent current density by increased to single cell test time. After 15 hours, TiN coated specimen recovered a little to current density and then current density slowly dropped down.

Therefore, TiN coating layer has a support to excellent passive film. So, passive film reduced corrosion velocity under a sulfuric acid condition within PEMFC environment.

(a) Non coated STS316

(b) TiN coated STS316

Fig. 5 Result of single cell test for Non-coated and TiN coated STS316 metallic bipolar plate.

4. Conclusions

STS316 materials for bipolar plate of PEMFC is required coating to increase corrosion resistance.

TiN-coated STS316 specimen has a good passive film. This film on STS316 reacted to increase corrosion resistance than Non-coated STS316.

And TiN coated STS316 specimens as a bipolar plate of PEMFC was found to satisfy the DOE requirement.

Therefore, PEMFC bipolar plate for the STS316 in order to apply to a long life and durability has to apply for the TiN coating process.

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